

OPTIMIZING AWARENESS IN GREEN COMPUTING INITIATIVES

Kanwaldip Kaur

P.G. Department of Computer Science, Mata Gujri College, Fatehgarh Sahib

ABSTRACT

Green computing (or green IT) refers to the design, use, and disposal of computers and IT infrastructure in a way that reduces environmental impact. This includes energy-efficient hardware, sustainable software, virtualization, cloud computing, and responsible e-waste management.

Goals of Awareness in Green Computing

1. **Educate** users on environmental impacts of technology.
2. **Promote** energy-efficient hardware/software choices.
3. **Encourage** sustainable behavior (e.g., turning off devices, reducing printing).
4. **Influence** corporate and public policy decisions.
5. **Inspire** innovation in eco-friendly tech.

From home computers to enterprise systems, client to server machines, attention in “Green Computing” has moved the research into energy saving techniques during recent years. It deals with reduction in carbon footprints and power saving. Energy is wasted in abundance at various data centres and data servers as well as in clouds. The research in the direction of green computing is much wider. In the paper a thorough study has been done on different issues of green computing in all spheres of society. Surveys have been analysed about green computing initiatives across the globe and interesting facts came out. Current trends, challenges and future trends in green computing are explored. Further research is necessary to explore Green ICT so that people from different professions get benefits. In today’s scenario global warming is becoming a great threat, so with a view to that it is the need of the hour to make people aware about Green Computing.

Keywords: Green Computing, Green ICT, Client and Server Machines, Carbon Footprints

1. INTRODUCTION

Green Computing means eco-friendly and responsible use of computers and other technologies such as networking devices, storage devices, printers, monitors and so on. It is the study of manufacturing, designing and disposing of computing devices in such a way so that they don’t have negative impact on the environment. Reducing energy wastage, developing efficient computing devices, reducing irresponsible use of devices, motivating recycling of devices and papers are all parts of green computing technologies. One of the reasons for Global warming is human activities and the recognition of these activities is increasing. Green Computing practices tackle the environment issues that have been there because of computing devices. Environmental sustainability can only be achieved with these practices only. The burning of fossil fuels produces power which is required to run a device. It has a high amount of carbon footprint. Fossil fuels are the resources of the energy which are non-renewable. The emissions from burning of these fuels have carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide. They have very bad effect on human health. Emission of CO₂ from fossil fuels total about 28 billion tonnes per year worldwide. Approximately 43% of this is from oil and 38% from coal. Per year power stations’ running on black coal produces CO₂ emissions of

about 7 million tonnes. In office environments monitors have the highest energy consumption. The electricity costs can be reduced significantly by managing the usage of these devices. When a computer is active, on an average it requires between 36W and 250W. E-waste is becoming the rapidly-growing type of waste. Most electronics contain non-biodegradable materials. These types of materials can harm human life badly. Lead, mercury and toxic materials are found in most electronics. According to StEP, a record of 48.9 million metric tons of e-waste was generated in 2012 worldwide. This can cause serious environmental problems that should be tackled properly.

2. IMPLEMENTATION OF GREEN COMPUTING

It is a necessity to find out the solution for the above mentioned problems due to e-waste. It becomes the responsibility of every individual and institution to take proper care for reducing the negative impacts of this problem. Green Computing is the best way to overcome this problem. Following are some ways how green computing should be implemented:

1.1 Computer Devices: There are different kinds of monitors available in the market these days. LCD monitors consumes less energy as compared to CRT monitors. Laptop computers require a fraction of the energy of desktop computers because of the following reasons :

1. Laptops are more frequently turned off and unplugged.
2. They require less power.
3. To preserve battery power, they go into low power mode more quickly.

3.1 Computer Ethics: As technology advances, computers are having a greater impact on society. People should be educated about the basic computer ethics. They should learn the facts to be followed while using computer. These are :

1. One should turn off the computer when not in use.
2. Put the computer on sleep mode if nobody is using it.
3. Always use the 80 plus certified power supply units for the computer.
4. Avoid using Screen Savers rather than turn off the monitor.

3.2 Cloud Computing: Cloud computing is where software applications, data and potentially even artificial intelligence are accessed over the Internet. Cloud computing has many advantages, one of which is enabling anybody to obtain the environmental benefits of virtualization. Most servers in company data centres run at 30 per cent capacity, most cloud vendor servers run at 80 per cent capacity or more. By choosing to cloud compute by adopting online computer processing power in the form of PaaS or IaaS companies may therefore potentially reduce their carbon footprint. As well as allowing server capacity to run at more optimal energy efficiency, cloud computing can also remove the need for most users to run high-power PCs and laptops.

3.3 Desktop Virtualization: In Virtualization, one physical server hosts many virtual servers. It reduces the carbon footprint because of the usage of multiple computer devices. Hosting multiple virtual servers on a small number of servers is a far better approach which reduces the power consumption to a great extent. Virtualization makes better hardware usage and reduces demands for energy.

3.4 Telecommunication: There are many services available in telecommunication through which green computing can be implemented such as teleconference and telepresence.

Culture of working from home is increasing these days which reduces travelling resulting in the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. It also reduces heat, lighting and lower costs for office.

3.5 E-Waste Cycling: There should be a trend of recycling of E-wastes like old computers and monitors. Rather than disposing them, one must try to recycle these wastes. There are municipal and private recycling bodies available one should submit these waste material with these organisations. We can refurbish old computers and servers instead of purchasing new devices. Print only what we need and use of recycled content paper whenever possible is another good practice. Most printers today have a two-sided printing option which can dramatically reduce paper consumption. Recycled used ink and toner cartridges may also be used.

3.6 Power Management: Power management can be done by ensuring that Computers systems are turn off when there is no need of these devices. Laptops should be put on sleep mode in idle times. There must be provisions in software too of less power consumption. There must be built in power saving features. Energy Consumption can be analysed by Energy star labels. Appliances having high star rating should be purchased. More-efficient processors are another critical energy-saving element, as Intel, Advanced Micro Devices, and Sun Microsystems all have adopted the green religion.

3.7 Eco Friendly Approach: Reliability about the use of green materials in computing is perhaps the biggest single challenge for the electronics industry. Lead-tin solder use of today is very malleable making it an ideal shock absorber. So far, more brittle replacement solders have yet to show the same reliability in real-world applications. Replacements like the front-runner, a tin/copper/silver alloy, also require higher melting temperatures, which can affect chip life.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Various surveys have been conducted and many results came about the daily usage of computers, hours per day computer used, number of computers/laptops owned, Number of pages printed per day, number of people switching to low power consumption mode, awareness about risk to environment due to global warming. A few of them have been elaborated below:

Out of 1000 persons , about 150 persons uses computer for less than 1 hour per day ,around 660 persons uses computer for 1 to 5 hours per day ,about 155 uses 5 to 10 hours per day and about 41 persons for more than 10 hours. As it is seen that about 660 persons out of 1000 are using computer for 1 to 5 hours which is the maximum should be made aware about the right usage of computer. They must be aware about the power saving approaches so that they can

make best use of computer and utilize it maximum. The reduction in consumption of electricity would definitely reduce the energy usage to a great extent.

It is seen that around 89% of the users print an average of less than 10 pages per day. Around 6% prints between 10 to 50 pages and around 5% between 50 to 100 pages. So there must be provisions for ink utilizations. Certain methods must be used so that there be maximum utilization of ink used to print a page, so that no. of cartridges used are less which lead to reduction in e-waste as well.

Out of 1000 people about 427 which is 43% are aware about the present issues related with global warming. There are so many issues concerned with global warming like carbon footprints, climate change patterns, rapid degradation of non-renewable energy resources and many more. Around 7% are unaware about these issued and around 4% are not even concerned. So there is lack of awareness. If awareness will be there, we can think of the change. These were the results of the surveys done on literate people. The results can be down if it is to be done on common masses. So it is mandatory to make people aware about the present scenario and the future results. We need to do improvements in our daily habits regarding usage of technology and power consumption.

REFERENCES

1. Green Computing Endeavor in Higher Educational Institutes – a noble initiative towards Sustainable IT Infrastructure, Shalabh Agarwal, Archana Vimal, Saima Ghosh, Asoke Nath, Journal of Computing(USA), Vol 4 ,issues 5, May, ISSN-9617, Page-217-222,2012

2. A Study of Green Computing: The Future Computing and Eco- Friendly Technology, By S.V.S.S Lakshmi.
3. Green Computing and Green Technology based teaching learning and administration in Higher Education Institutions: Shalabh Agarwal ,Shreya Goswami, Asoke Nath, International Journal of Computer Applications(IJCA), Vol 76, No. 7,(August),Pp. 35-41(2013)
4. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Green_computing, accessed during May- July 2008
5. <http://static.googleusercontent.com/media/www.google.com/en//green/pdfs/google-green-computing.pdf>
6. <http://www.csi-india.org/green-computing>, accessed during May- July 2008
7. <http://www.techno-preneur.net/information-desk/sciencetech-magazine/2007/nov07/GreenComputing.pdf>, accessed during May- July 2008
8. <http://www.wipro.co.in/products/greenpc/html/0007clip.htm>, accessed during May- July 2008
9. Gary B. S (2002)Discovering Computers: Concepts for a Digital World, Complete Shelly Cashman Series: Complete
10. Sivaharan, T, Blair, G. and Coulson, G (2005), GREEN: A Configurable and Re-configurable Publish-Subscribe Middleware for Pervasive Computing - lecture Notes in Computer Science, 2005 – Springer